

To Study the Impact of Human Resource Management Practices of Employees in Medium Scale Manufacturing Industries

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Abstract

Human Resource Management (HRM) is an approach to manage human resources in any organization. Human resource is a group of individuals who make up the working force of an organization, industry or any business sector. Since an organization is a body of people; their recruitment, skill development, motivation for higher studies and maintain their level of commitment to the organization are all its core activities. HRM is engaged in providing human dignity to employees, considering their capacity, potential, talents, accomplishment, motivation, skill, commitment, abilities, and so on, so that their presence is recognized as valuable human beings. The main component of an organization is its human resource or "people at work". The current study has been conducted in various Medium Scale Manufacturing Industries in Ludhiana, India, which are following the HRM practices effectively. The study involves exploring the contribution of humans and their management efforts in medium scale industries with the objective of improving their Business Performance. The relationship between the various factors of the study i.e. the input factors with the performance measures has been assessed and validated using different statistical tools.

Keywords: Business performance, Human Resource Management, Indian, Manufacturing Industries.

1. INTRODUCTION

'Human Management' is very important and challenging job because of the dynamic nature of the people. No two people are similar in terms of mental abilities, knowledge, feelings and behavior. People are responsive; they feel, think and act so they cannot be managed as a machine or shifted and changed as a template in the workspace. Therefore, HR managers must tackle them delicately and tactfully. Human resources management is a strategic and comprehensive business function that enables its working staff to contribute efficiently and productively to the overall benefit of the organization and the achievement of the organization's goals and objectives. (Uyar and Deniz, 2012).

The history of the development of human resources management in India is comparative of the recent origin. In the modern sense, it has developed only after independence. Although the need and

importance of labour officer was recognised as early as 1929, the appointment of officers to solve labour and social problems gained momentum only after the Law of the Factories Act of 1948 came into force. Section 49 of the law requires the appointment of social welfare officers in companies with more than 500 workers. In the beginning the government was dealing only with limited aspects of the well-being of labour. The management of labour and well-being has subsequently been modernised to manage staff over time, which has evolved as a human resources management, as is known in today's world. Figure 1 shows the Evolution of HRM with time span.

Figure 1 Evolution of HRM

(Source:<https://hrdictionary.files.wordpress.com/2012/10/evolution-of-hrm3.jpg>)

1.1 Major Objectives of HRM

The main objective of HRM is to ensure the availability of a competent and desirable workforce for an organization. Beyond this, there are other goals. Specifically, the objectives of HRM are fourfold: Societal, Organization, Functional and Personal as shown in Figure 2.

Objectives of HRM

Figure 2 Objectives of HRM

(Source:

<https://www.slideshare.net/raiuniversity/mba-ii-hrm-ul-1-hrm-basics>)

a. Personal Objectives:

To assist Employees in achieving their personal goals, at least in so far as these goals enhance individual's contribution to the organization. Personal objectives of employees must be maintained, retained and motivated.

b. Functional Objectives:

These objectives help to maintain the contribution of a particular department at an appropriate level that meets requirements of the organization. Workforce is thus required to be adjusted

to match the demands of organization. The service level of the department concerned should be customized to suit the business requirements of the organization.

c. Organizational Objectives:

The organizational objectives acknowledge the function of human resource management in organizational effectiveness. HRM isn't an end in itself; it's just an effective way to help the business with its main objectives. Basically the HR department is out there to serve the rest of the organization.

d. Societal Objectives:

To be ethically & socially responsible for the needs and challenges of society while minimizing the negative impact of such demands upon the organization to use their resources for society's benefits in ethical ways may lead to restriction.

e. Other objectives:

- Achieve the main organizational goals by creating and using a skilled and motivated work force.
- Establish and maintain an organizational structure and required working relationship between all members of the organization.
- Develop coordination between individuals and groups in the organization to ensure the integration of the organization.
- Creating opportunities and co-ordination for individual or group development to secure the growth of the organization.
- Attain effective use of human resources to achieve organizational goals.
- Identify and meet individual and group needs by providing adequate and fair wages, incentives, employee benefits and social security, and measures to induce work, prestige, recognition, security, status.
- Maintain high morale of employees and human relationships by

maintaining and improving the various conditions and facilities.

- Strengthen and evaluate human resources continuously by providing training and development programs.
- Consider and contribute to minimize socio-economic issues such as unemployment, under employment, inequality in income and wealth distribution, and improving the welfare of society by empowering women and disadvantaged sections of society.
- Ensure voice expression and voice management.
- Ensure fair, acceptable and effective leadership.
- Provide better working conditions and facilities and also create a favorable atmosphere for maintaining employment stability.
- Creating and using a skilled and motivated workforce, creating and maintaining a stable organizational structure, creating facilities, achieving effective utilization of resources, identifying and meeting individual and group needs.
- Maintaining high employee morale and freedom of expression ensuring fair, acceptable and effective leadership terms and conditions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Singh (2010) examined the relationship between HRM practices and organisational culture in private sector organisations operating in India. Organizational culture is evolving in the Indian environment along with global working values. This study was based on different respondents working in two private sector organisations. Although human resource management practices in these organisations differ widely, the

relationship between HRM practices and organizational culture is significant. Planning, recruitment, selection, training and development, job evaluation, career management and awards are essential to all dimensions of organizational culture.

Jianfeng et. al, (2011) explained that human capital is a key factor for production in the 21st century, becoming an important resource that defines economic development and competition in business. At the moment, Chinese businesses face serious challenges, but also opportunities. From this study, it was found that the Chinese companies will have to update their ideas, rearrange the structure of human resources, strengthen staff training and learning and introduce advanced human resource management techniques and tools to achieve strategic goals.

Kaur (2014) examined the impact of human resource practices on the satisfaction of the work and the organizational commitment of the employees in the production industry in Punjab, India. Data was collected and the analysis of the data was performed by correlation tests and regression analysis. The results show that human resource practices have a positive impact on the level of job satisfaction and organisational commitment of employees. The organization should focus on increasing motivation, job satisfaction and organizational commitment through rewards and recognition. Prizes can be monetary or non-monetary, depending on the results of employees.

Zehret. al, (2016) analysed the results from the tests conducted on the impact of strategic human resources practices on organizational innovation and the knowledge management capacities of

companies (knowledge sharing and implementation of knowledge). Data was collected from various industries. The results of the regression analysis underlined that only some practices in the strategic human resource have a predictive power of organizational innovation. In addition, a similar model is observed between strategic human resource practices and knowledge management capacities of companies. Overall, the findings spoke about the importance of systems for compensation, training and evaluation of performance as predictors of dependent variables.

Homayounfard and Safakish (2016) have studied and suggested that human resource management (HRM) is a subject to a level of organizational improvement and strategic change. This study improved the understanding of HRM processes in organizational terms. It contributed to the existing literature on processes and decision-making in the field of HRM. A theoretical model was developed that assessed the needs of all organizations related to HRM, especially in projects of large size. The model was used as a tool for evaluating the employees responsible at both the organizational level and project level. This research has created a new practical framework that reveals the factors influencing human resource indices in the project oriented companies.

Wicher (2016) analysed and presented current human resource management practices in Chinese manufacturing companies. The work was originally a research study that compared human resource management in Chinese and Czech manufacturing companies. A questionnaire on specific aspects of HRM, such as recruitment, evaluation of work and remuneration, training and

development, was drafted to obtain the necessary data. Data obtained from different Chinese companies were analysed. Descriptive statistical data and variation analysis were applied to achieve the most beneficial results. The results show significant differences in the different aspects of HRM, depending on the size and ownership of the monitored companies. The results, followed by discussion and consequences, underline the importance of correct practices that implement all aspects of HRM in a functional complex.

3. METHODOLOGY

To study the effect of human resource management practices in medium industries, a descriptive-analytical inferential approach is used where research is to form a database from which characteristics or relations of population are to be inferred. In this research, the information is described and analyzed in order to obtain results.

The present study focuses on evaluating the impact of practicing HRM approach on medium scale manufacturing industries in Ludhiana. The strategic success factors that will be found using various statistical tools will emphasize the contribution of the human resources to the realization and achievement of main organizational objective i.e. improved Business Performance. The steps to be followed in the study are shown below in Figure 3

Figure 3. Block diagram of Research Methodology

In the current study, in order to identify the benefits realized by the effective approach to human resources management, it becomes imperative to scrutinize carefully the implementation of different success factors and performance measures achieved. In this study, five input factors for successful implementation (A, B, C, D and E) and five performance indicators (P, Q, R, S and T) have been identified as important for analyzing the impact of successful variables on performance of the presented model. Table-1 shows various input factors and performance measures.

Table- 1 Description of Inputs and Performance Measure Categories

Input Factors	Performance Measures
A- Organization Role: Selection, Policies and Promotions	P- Overall Business Productivity
B- Training Culture: Workers, Supervisors and Managerial Staff	Q- Multi Skilling
C- Work Environment: Inter Departmental Relationship	R- Work Culture Improvement
D- Job Satisfaction and Morale	S- Employee Satisfaction
E- Self-interest of Employees	T- Staff Turnover

3.1 Tool used for the study

Questionnaire on Human Resources Management (HRM) practices has been designed to assess the responses of

various medium scale manufacturing industries in Ludhiana.

In HRM questionnaire, the categories of inputs refer to organizational initiatives for the implementation of human resources management initiatives and other human-related issues, while the performance measures deal with the indicators of excellence in production, realized as a result of the successful practicing of HRM policies to achieve organizational goals.

In order to assess the degree of use of the various organizational initiatives for the implementation of a success factor in human resource management and efficiency measures, a four-point Likert scale, as described in Table 2, is used in this study.

Table-2 Likert scale used in the study

Organizational Initiatives (Inputs)	Performance Measures (Outputs)
1 Not at all	1 Nominal Gain (< 10%)
2 To some extent	2 Reasonable Gain (10-30%)
3 To large extent	3 High Gain (30-45%)
4 To full extent	4 Very High Gain (>45%)

Validation of Questionnaire was done from recourse persons of industries as well as Academicians. Respondents for questionnaires were: General Managers (GM), Additional General Manager (AGM), Human Resources Managers (Managers of Personnel), Human Resources Officers, Technical Managers etc. The responses thus received were compiled and analysed critically to ascertain the performance of the medium scale manufacturing industries in Ludhiana regarding various HRM related issues.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A test of reliability on the measurement instrument has been carried out to determine its ability to receive consistent measurements. Cronbach's α is the basic formula for determining the reliability based on internal consistency. Therefore, the assessment of Cronbach's α for different categories, i.e. the input factors (independent variables) and the performance measures (dependent variables) of a constructed questionnaire have been calculated to ascertain the reliability of the input and output data collected from medium scale manufacturing industries in Ludhiana through the HRM questionnaire. Table-3 shows Cronbach's α values for different input factors and performance measures calculated using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences).

Table-3 Cronbach's α Values for Input Factors and Performance Measures

Input Factors	Cronbach's α value	Performance Measures	Cronbach's α value
A	0.807	P	0.849
B	0.829	Q	0.802
C	0.769	R	0.775
D	0.720	S	0.870
E	0.788	T	0.746

It was observed from Table-3 that the values of Cronbach's α for all input factors and performance measures were greater than 0.65, which shows significantly high reliability of data for different input and output factors.

Table-4 Covariance Values of Input Factors and Performance Measures

	A	B	C	D	E	P	Q	R	S	T
A	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
B	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
C	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
D	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
E	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
P	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
Q	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
R	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
S	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
T	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00

C	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
D	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
E	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
P	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00
Q	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00
R	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
S	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00
T	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00

Further to obtain more confidence in collected data, Covariance Validity Analysis was conducted for checking the covariance of all the Input Factors (A, B, C, D and E) and Performance Measures (P, Q, R, S and T) and it was again observed that all the respective covariance values within the group are more than the value of covariance outside the group as shown in Table 4.

4.2 Strategic Success Factors of HRM for meeting the Organizational Objectives

To find out the effective relationship between the Input Factors and Performance Measures, the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient 'r' was calculated. The contribution of a specific Input Factor to the realization of different Performance Measures was determined as shown in Table-5.

Table-5 Values of Pearson's Correlation for Input Factors and Performance Measures

	P	Q	R	S	T	
A	Pearson Correlation	.583**	.512**	.486**	.613**	.541**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.001	.000	.000
	N	43	43	43	43	43
B	Pearson Correlation	.598**	.614**	.630**	.557**	.555**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	43	43	43	43	43
C	Pearson Correlation	.582**	.393**	.482**	.496**	.639**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.009	.001	.001	.000
	N	43	43	43	43	43

D	Pearson Correlation	.575**	.504**	.446**	.650**	.600**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001	.003	.000	.000
E	N	43	43	43	43	43
	Pearson Correlation	.714**	.499**	.573**	.378*	.541**
E	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001	.000	.012	.000
	N	43	43	43	43	43

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed)

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed)

Table-5 indicates that there is a Strong Correlation of Employee Satisfaction (S) with Organization Role (A) which clearly interpreted that proper promotion channel, selection processes and HR policies play a crucial role in satisfaction among employees (0.613**). Proper Training of employees (B) helped to improve the Work Culture (R) (0.630**). Proper Work Environment (C) leads to reduced Staff Turnover (T) (0.639**). When the employee is satisfied with his job and has high morale (D), Employee Satisfaction (S) is achieved (0.650**) and Self Interest of Employees (E) helps to improve the Overall Business Productivity (P) (0.714**).

Further to understand the inter relationship between various performance measures with specific input factors 'Multiple Regression Analysis' as shown in Table 6 was conducted.

As, Multiple Regression Analysis is a statistical tool for finding the relationship among variables. It includes many techniques for modeling and analyzing the variables, when the focus is on the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables.

The notations used and their meanings are given below:

- p - Level of significance;
- r- Pearson Correlation Coefficient;
- β - Regression Coefficient (β Coefficient);
- and
- R - Multiple Correlation Coefficient

Table-6 Multiple Regressions among HRM Input Factors and Performance Measures

Performance Measures	Input factors	Beta value β	t-value	Significance (p-value)	R/R ² -value	F-value
P	E	0.480	3.206	0.003	0.755/0.570	9.817
Q	B	0.499	2.241	0.031	0.641/0.411	5.168
R	B	0.517	2.412	0.021	0.675/0.455	6.179
	E	0.287	1.698	0.098		
S	D	0.457	2.231	0.032	0.683/0.467	6.476
T	C	0.421	2.458	0.019	0.714/0.510	7.688
	D	0.374	1.906	0.064		

The result of Multiple Regression implies that there is a significant role of various Success Factors in the Table-6 with respect to Performance Measures reported. The study provides empirical evidence of a strong role for human resource input factors and performance measures.

It has been observed that P-Overall Business Productivity is associated with E-Self Interest of Employees for the realization of the overall manufacturing performance enhancements. The results indicates that Q-Multi-skilling is associated with B-Training Culture (of Workers, Supervisors and Managers) to improve the employees skills and abilities. Both Training Culture-B and Self Interest of employees-E have strong bond with Work Culture Improvement-R to improve quality of work and reduction in failures as well as improved work conditions. D-Job Satisfaction and Morale have strong relation with S-Employee Satisfaction for the improvement in job security, health and safety of employees. T-Staff Turnover is associated with C-Work Environment (Inter-Departmental relationships) and also with D-Job Satisfaction and Morale) to

ensure minimum Staff Turnover and reduction in unsatisfied workforce.

4.3 LEVEL OF IMPORTANCE OF VARIOUS HRM ISSUES EVOLVED IN IMPROVING BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

To further examine the level of importance of the various issues related to human resource management evolved in improving organizational effectiveness, z-distribution or the z-test is applied. The z-test or z-statistic follows a normal distribution. A z-test is a statistical test used to determine whether two population means are different when the variances are known and the sample size is large. The test statistic is assumed to have a [normal distribution](#), and parameters such as [standard deviation](#) should be known for accurately performing the z-test. The z-test is used where sample size is greater than 30 because according to the central limit theorem, as the sample size gets larger, the samples are assumed to be approximately normally distributed. (Source: <http://www.investopedia.com/terms/z/z-test.asp>).

$$Z = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu}{\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}}$$

Where:

\bar{x} - Sample Mean

μ - Population Mean

σ - Standard Deviation Mean

n - Sample Size

The level of importance of different issues has been measured from the values of mean and the significance level has been tested on the basis of z-statistics. Table-7 show level of importance of different HRM sub-issues.

Table-7 Level of importance of HRM sub-issues

Issues	Mean	Standard Deviation	z-statistics
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Organizational Role Issues			
Provide relevant information about the organization and job to the candidates at the time of recruitment?	3.488372	0.505781	3.7345*
Select the candidates on merit basis?	3.465116	0.591561	2.935473*
Places the right person in right job?	3.534884	0.504685	4.346256*
Have well planned and structured HR policies that cover common HR management responsibilities?	3.488372	0.592496	3.18793*
Benchmark the competitors HR policies?	3.44186	0.547824	2.891781*
Formulate improvement actions in policies on the basis of benchmarking?	3.534884	0.549841	3.989311*
Follow a predefined written promotion channel for promoting employees?	3.488372	0.550848	3.428966*
Update its promotion plans at regular intervals to motivate its employees for better performance?	3.488372	0.592496	3.18793*
Training Culture Issues			
What percentage of employees is involved in training programs every year?	3.674419	0.565725	5.492853*
Does your organization's HR department conduct regular seminars and hands on training for employees?	3.604651	0.494712	5.357594*
Whether emphasis is laid on achieving multi-skilling of workers and supervisors?	3.697674	0.464701	7.014766*
Do you have training programs for	3.604651	0.540702	4.901895*

higher-level managers?			
Whether organization encourages employees to make decisions regarding continuous productivity improvements?	3.534884	0.504685	4.346256*
Work Environment Issues			
Are there regular meetings of supervisors of all departments collectively with workers at regular intervals?	3.581395	0.499169	5.004599*
Does your organization have good Inter-Departmental employee to employee relationship?	3.55814	0.547824	4.28206*
Are the employees motivated to work collectively with other departments towards achieving common goals?	3.55814	0.502486	4.668421*
Whether the supervisors of a department discuss the schedule before finalizing with other departments?	3.55814	0.502486	4.668421*
Does your organization make efforts to create a sense of belongingness among employees?	3.55814	0.502486	4.668421*
Job Satisfaction and Morale Issues			
Does your organization value the contribution of employees to its well-being?	3.534884	0.504685	4.346256*
Are the employees satisfied with various welfare facilities like subsidized food, recreational facilities, housing, medical aids, additional family support, education to children, etc.?	3.581395	0.499169	5.004599*
Does your	3.627907	0.489083	5.7307*

organization recognize the career growth needs of its employees?			
Does your organization care about its employees opinions?	3.581395	0.499169	5.004599*
Are the rewards and incentives fairly distributed and strictly linked to employees' performance?	3.534884	0.504685	4.346256*
Self Interest of Employees Issues			
Is every employee of your organization interested to help new workers, even when not asked to do so?	3.534884	0.504685	4.346256*
Does every employee willingly stay late at work whenever the organization requires?	3.604651	0.540702	4.901895*
Are the employees always interested to make suggestions for improvements?	3.581395	0.499169	5.004599*
Whether your company encourages employees to volunteer for their self-interest works?	3.534884	0.504685	4.346256*
Whenever a need arise, do the employees show self-interest to protect the reputation of the organization?	3.604651	0.494712	5.357594*
Does every employee interestedly take up extra duties and responsibilities?	3.604651	0.494712	5.357594*
Z critical (0.05) = 1.645 * Significant at 5% level Z critical (0.01) = 2.464 **Significant at 1% level			

Results of investigation from Table-7 show clearly that calculated z-value is more than table value of z at the level of significance adopted. Further, those sub-

issues having higher value of z are considered more relevant to the study, which demonstrates that placing the right person in right job, formulating improvement actions in policies on the basis of benchmarking and providing relevant information about the job and organization to the candidates at the time of recruitment are important sub factors that contribute to organizational role for improving the business. Multi-skilling of workers and supervisors, more emphasis on training of employees and regular seminars and hands on training for employees conducted by the HR department contribute to the training culture issue in order to achieve organizational goals. The work environment contributes through regular meetings of supervisors of all departments collectively with workers at regular intervals, motivation of employees to work collectively with other departments towards achieving common goals, discussion of schedules by supervisors before finalizing with other departments and sense of belongingness among employees. Job satisfaction and morale is justified by recognizing the career growth needs of employees by the organization, providing various welfare facilities like subsidized food, recreational facilities, housing, medical aids, additional family support, education to children, etc. and caring about the employee's opinions by the organization. Self-interest of employees is justified by employees interestedly taking up extra duties and responsibilities, self-interest of employees to protect the reputation of the organization and the interest of employees to make suggestions for improvements. Similarly, to find out the level of importance of the HRM factors taken in

the study, the z-test is applied factor wise as shown in Table-8.

Table-8 Level of importance of HRM factors

Issues	Mean	Standard Deviation	z-statistics
<i>Organizational Role Issues</i>	3.491279	0.554441	3.441081*
<i>Training Culture Issues</i>	3.623256	0.514105	5.39253*
<i>Work Environment Issues</i>	3.562791	0.51089	4.651256*
<i>Job Satisfaction and Morale Issues</i>	3.572093	0.499358	4.880685*
<i>Self Interest of Employees Issues</i>	3.577519	0.506444	4.882578*
Z critical (0.05) = 1.645 * Significant at 5% level Z critical (0.01) = 2.464 **Significant at 1% level			

The Success Factors that contribute to achieve the desired Performance Measures in medium scale manufacturing industries under study form z-test analysis are-

- Training Culture (5.39253*)
- Self Interest of Employees (4.882578*)
- Job Satisfaction and Morale (4.880685*)

5. CONCLUSION

From the results obtained through Multiple Regression Analysis and z-test analysis, various Success Factors that contribute in achieving the main objectives of the organizations were found. Results from both Multiple Regression and z-test were studied collectively and finally, three Strategic Success Factors were found namely Training Culture, Self Interest of Employees and Job Satisfaction and Morale that contribute in achieving high Business Performance as shown in Table-9.

Table-9 Strategic Success Factors of HRM

Multiple Regression Analysis		z-test analysis		Overall Strategic Success Factors of Study
Performance Measures	Success Factors	Issues	z-statistics (Success Factors)	
<i>Overall Business Productivity</i>	Self Interest of Employees	<i>Organizational Role</i>	3.441081*	Training Culture (TC)
<i>Multi Skilling</i>	Training Culture	<i>Training Culture</i>	5.39253*	Self Interest of Employees (SI)
<i>Work Culture Improvement</i>	Training Culture, Self Interest of Employees	<i>Work Environment</i>	4.651256*	Job Satisfaction and Morale (JSM)
<i>Employee Satisfaction</i>	Job Satisfaction and Morale	<i>Job Satisfaction and Morale</i>	4.880685*	-
<i>Staff Turnover</i>	Work Environment, Job Satisfaction and Morale	<i>Self Interest of Employees</i>	4.882578*	-

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